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Investigation of the Relationship Between the Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem Perceptions and Leadership Orientations of the Faculty of Sports Sciences Students

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Abstract

This research was carried out to investigate of the relationship between the two-dimensional self-esteem perceptions and leadership orientations of the students of the faculty of sports sciences. In this context, the relational survey model, which is consistent with the main purpose of the study, was used in this quantitative study. A total of 323 students, 125 females and 198 males at the Faculty of Sports Sciences of Bartın University constitute the sample of the research. Convenience sampling method, one of the non-probabilistic sampling approaches, was used in the selection of the research group. Questionnaire form was used as data collection tool and this form consisted of three parts. The first part includes the “Personal Information Form,” the second part includes the “Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem: Self-Liking/Self-Competence Scale” and the third part includes the “Multidimensional Leadership Orientations Scale.” The descriptive statistics of the raw data obtained through the questionnaire form were first calculated by considering the data type. Then, the reliability of the scales related to the obtained data were investigated, and the difference and correlation tests were used in the statistical evaluation. In this direction, it has been determined that there are significant correlations within the scope of age and family income level variables. However, there was no significant relationship within the scope of personal income level variable. On the other hand, it was found that there are significant differences in the scope of department and actively doing sports variables. However, it was observed that there were no significant differences in the scope of gender, grade, and place of residence variables. On the other hand, it was determined that there were positive and moderately significant correlations between the participants’ scores of self-liking and political leadership, human resources leadership, charismatic leadership and structural leadership. In addition, it was found that there were positive and moderately significant correlations between the self-competence scores of the participants and the scores of political leadership, charismatic leadership and structural leadership. On the other hand, it was understood that there was a statistically significant positive and low-level correlation between the participants’ self-competence scores and their human resources leadership scores. As a result, it can be said that as the self-esteem of the participants increases, their leadership orientation also increases. In this context, it can be said that increasing the self-esteem of the participants is an important concept in the context of leadership orientations.

Keywords: Self-Esteem, Leadership Orientation, Faculty of Sport Sciences

1. Introduction

The self is explained as a structure formed by the combination of values, goals and ideals by revealing the individual's behavior styles (Ozoglu, 2019). According to Koknel (1982), the self is formed by the coming together of the individual's opinions about himself/herself. The self is a subjective part of personality and is each individual's self-evaluation of who they are. The person tries to get to know his/herself by seeking answers to questions such as what his/her purpose, what he/she can do and what he/she values. Therefore, the self includes all the characteristics, value judgments, thoughts, beliefs, abilities, possibilities, goals and expectations of the individual and represents an unstable structure.

In its most general sense, self-esteem is defined as the extent to which an individual evaluates himself/herself positively (Kagıtcıbası, 2014). Self-esteem covers how the individual sees and evaluates himself/herself. That is, it constitutes the emotional side of the self-system. In addition, it is accepted that self-esteem is open to changes due to its relative nature (Gelbal et al., 2010; Tufan, 1990). Yorukoglu (1985) explains self-esteem as a state of appreciation that emerges when the individual accepts the self-image that he/she has reached based on his/her self-evaluations.

According to Coopersmith (1967), self-esteem is based on the evaluations that an individual makes and maintains about himself/herself, and its foundations are laid in the early stages of life. He stated that this means an attitude of approval or disapproval, as well as related to how talented, important and valuable the individual sees himself or herself. On the other hand, according to Rosenberg, self-esteem includes positive or negative attitudes towards the self. However, two different connotations emerge for self-esteem. These are (Rosenberg, 1965):

High self-esteem: There is a view that the individual is good enough. The individual feels that he/she is a valuable person, accepts himself/herself as he/she is and respects himself/herself. This situation should not be perceived as individuals expecting any admiration from others or as individuals seeing themselves as superior to others. Individuals with high self-esteem are aware of their skills, capacities and deficiencies, recognize their own limits, and constantly seek change, development and success.

Low self-esteem: It expresses the feelings and attitudes of the individual towards his/her self such as rejection, dislike, abstention and dissatisfaction. Individuals with low self-esteem have less self-confidence and self-esteem than those with high self-esteem. They are often unaware of their own abilities and capacities.

Self-esteem affects people's daily functioning and the way they perform tasks. Some studies have shown that those with higher self-esteem perform better when tasked and can perform well under pressure in a high-intensity situation (Baumeister et al., 2003; Smith et al., 2007). Studies have determined that there is a similar relationship between self-esteem and sports performance. Studies on self-esteem and sports have shown that doing sports has a positive effect on self-esteem (Bowker, 2006; Collins et al., 2018; Slutzky and Simpkins, 2009). In line with all these researches, it can be stated that sports will positively affect the self-esteem of the individual and will help to cope with the problems in life.

The concept that forms the other area of our research is leadership. The origin of the word leader comes from the Anglo-Saxon etymology "laed" and means way, direction. The verb form of the word "laeden" means to travel. Therefore, the leader; it can be defined as the person who guides the journey and guides other passengers during the journey (Kets de Vries, 2001).

To share a more concrete definition of the concept of leadership, "Leadership; it is the privilege of taking responsibility for different levels of authority to manage the actions of others for the purposes of organizations. The leader should be able to take responsibility for all initiatives, regardless of successful or unsuccessful discrimination, influencing the actions of others under any circumstances and guiding them (Roberts, 1988). In this context, Yukl compiled some of the leadership definitions in the literature and listed them as follows. Accordingly, leadership (Yukl, 2010);

- “the directing of the actions taken by the group towards a common goal.” (Hemphill and Coons, 1957)
- “it is an ascending influence within the organization and is more than a mechanical fit through routine instructions.” (Katz and Kahn, 1978)
- “the process of directing the actions of a group working together to achieve a goal.” (Rauch and Behling, 1984)
- “it is the process of giving meaning, direction and increasing willingness to joint efforts to achieve a goal.” (Jacobs and Jaques, 1990).

Yukl, who has important studies in the field of leadership, defined the Multidimensional Leadership approach as follows; “The Multidimensional Leadership Approach is a contingency theory based on the leader's determination of the appropriate leadership style according to the different developmental levels of the followers” (Yukl, 2010).

- Multidimensional Leadership Theory is based on the interaction of three basic concepts. These; The amount of directive given by the leader (task behavior exhibited by the leader),
- The amount of emotional support provided by the leader (relationship behavior exhibited by the leader),
- It is the level of development of the follower for a specific task (Hersey and Blanchard, 1988).

When the relevant literature was searched, no study was found that examined the relationship between two-dimensional self-esteem (self-liking and self-competence) and multi-dimensional leadership orientations (political leadership, human resources leadership, charismatic leadership, and structural leadership) in the context of the students of the Faculty of Sport Sciences. It is thought that the results to be reached in this direction will contribute to the relevant literature. In the light of all this literature, the purpose of the research is to examine the self-esteem and leadership characteristics of the students of the Faculty of Sport Sciences in terms of different demographic variables and to determine the relationship between self-esteem and leadership levels.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

Survey studies generally aim to describe the current situation related to the subject of the research by photographing (Buyukozturk et al., 2020). In addition, survey researchers are generally more interested in how the characteristics and opinions are distributed among the participants in the sample, rather than why they originate (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2006). In this context, the relational survey model, which is consistent with the main purpose, was used in this quantitative study.

2.2. Population and Sample

The universe of the research consists of 1383 (427 females and 956 males) students studying at the Faculty of Sports Sciences of Bartın University in the Fall Term of the 2021-2022 Academic Year. In this framework, a total of 323 students, 125 females and 198 males, constitute the sample of the research. Convenience sampling method, which is one of the non-probabilistic sampling approaches, was used in the creation of the sample. In this context, it is understood that the acceptable sample size for the research population has been reached (see Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

2.3. Data Collection Tools

The questionnaire form, which was prepared in accordance with the aims of the research, was applied to the participants on the internet between 04-19 October 2021 on a voluntary basis. During the implementation of the data collection tools, necessary explanations were given to the participants and it was ensured that they answered the questionnaire correctly. This form consists of three parts. The first part includes the “Personal Information Form,” the second part includes the “Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem: Self-Liking/Self-Competence Scale” and the third part includes the “Multidimensional Leadership Orientations Scale.”

2.3.1. Personal Information Form

In the Personal Information Form, there are statements about obtaining the participants' gender, age, department, grade, place of residence, actively doing sports status, monthly average personal income level and monthly average family income level (including personal income).

2.3.2. Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem: Self-Liking/Self-Competence Scale

The “Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem: Self-Liking/Self-Competence Scale” developed by Tafarodi and Swann (2001) to measure the self-esteem levels of the participants was adapted into Turkish by Dogan (2011). Data on the adaptation process of the scale were obtained from a total of 604 university students. The scale consists of 16 items and is in five-point Likert type. In addition, this scale; consists of two sub-dimensions (Self-Liking and Self-Competence). Psychometric properties of the scale in the adaptation study; item analysis, internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha), test-retest, confirmatory factor analysis and criterion-related validity methods. As a result, it has been determined that the scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool (Dogan, 2011).

2.3.3. Multidimensional Leadership Orientations Scale

The “Multidimensional Leadership Orientations Scale” was developed by Dursun, Gunay, and Yenel (2019) in order to determine the leadership orientations of the participants. Data on the development process of the scale were obtained from a total of 503 university students. The scale consists of 19 items and is in a five-point Likert type. In addition, this scale; consists of four sub-dimensions (Political Leadership, Human Resource Leadership, Charismatic Leadership and Structural Leadership). During the development of the scale, they were applied that exploratory and confirmatory factor analyzes and it was calculated that the internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha). As a result, it has been determined that the scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool (Dursun, Gunay, & Yenel, 2019).

2.4. Analysis of Data

IBM SPSS version 23.0 was used in the analysis of the data. First of all, descriptive statistics were calculated by considering the data type of the raw data in the questionnaire form obtained and transferred to the program. Then, t-Test and One Way ANOVA were used for difference tests, Pearson's Correlation and Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation analyzes were used for correlation tests in statistical evaluations according to whether the data obtained showed normal distribution or not. In this context, Hochberg's GT2 post-hoc test was applied for One-Way ANOVA, considering the homogeneity assumption and the distribution of the participants between groups. In calculating the reliability of the scales, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was taken into account within the framework of internal consistency. In addition, the level of significance was determined as 0.05 in statistical evaluations.

3. Results

In this part of the research, the findings obtained as a result of the analysis of the relevant data are presented and interpreted in the form of tables.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentages Regarding Variables

Variable	Group	f	%
Gender	Female	125	38.7
	Male	198	61.3
Department	Coaching Education	65	20.1
	Physical Education And Sports Teaching	57	17.6
	Recreation	90	27.9
	Sports Management	111	34.4
Grade	1st Grade	88	27.2
	2nd Grade	109	33.7

	3rd Grade	65	20.1
	4th Grade	61	18.9
Place of Residence	Village + Town + Community	51	15.8
	County Seat	86	26.6
	City Center	186	57.6
Actively Doing Sports Status	Yes	177	54.8
	No	146	45.2
Total		323	100,0

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that the number of male regarding the participants is approximately 1,6 times the number of female and the department with the highest number of participants is sports management. In addition, it is understood that the second grade has the highest number of participants and the fourth grade has the lowest number of participants. In addition, it is seen that the majority of the participants reside in the city center and actively engage in sports.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Age, Average Monthly Personal Income Level and Average Monthly Family Income Level Variables

Variable	n	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Age	32	20.643	20.000	1.9749	17.0	33.0	2.056	8.034
Average Monthly Personal Income Level	31	876.532	650.000	1159.7063	.0	8000.0	2.963	11.732
Average Monthly Family Income Level (Including Personal Income)	30	4501.127	3500.000	3410.2430	450.0	30000.0	3.478	17.768

According to Table 2, the mean age variable of the participants was 20,643 and the standard deviation was 1,9749; the mean of the monthly average personal income level variable is 876,532 Turkish Liras and its standard deviation is 1159,7063; it is seen that the average monthly family income level (including personal income) variable is 4501.127 Turkish Liras and its standard deviation is 3410,2430. In addition, when the skewness and kurtosis values of the table were examined, it was concluded that these variables did not exhibit normal distribution.

Table 3: Reliability Analysis Results of Scales

Subscales	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Self-Liking	.794	8
Self-Competence	.764	8
Political Leadership	.817	5
Human Resources Leadership	.811	5
Charismatic Leadership	.816	5
Structural Leadership	.799	4

According to Table 3, in the context of internal consistency coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) calculated within the scope of the research, subscales of self-liking ($\alpha=0.794$) and self-competence ($\alpha=0.764$) were found to be reliable within the framework of the two-dimensional self-esteem scale. In addition, it has been determined that the subscales of political leadership ($\alpha=0.817$), human resources leadership ($\alpha=0.811$), charismatic leadership ($\alpha=0.816$) and structural leadership ($\alpha=0.799$) are reliable within the framework of multidimensional leadership orientations scale.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of the Scales

Subscales	n	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Self-Liking	323	3.9923	4.1250	.70342	1.75	5.00	-.497	-.474
Self-Competence	323	3.5534	3.5000	.64483	1.38	5.00	.088	-.023
Political Leadership	323	3.9443	4.0000	.74741	1.00	5.00	-.499	.059
Human Resources Leadership	323	4.3907	4.6000	.61375	2.20	5.00	-1.077	.499
Charismatic Leadership	323	3.9901	4.0000	.71828	2.00	5.00	-.269	-.786
Structural Leadership	323	4.2082	4.2500	.69924	1.75	5.00	-.590	-.353

When Table 4 is examined, within the framework of the subscales of the two-dimensional self-esteem scale, the mean score of self-liking is 3,9923, the standard deviation is 0,70342, and the mean score of self-competence is 3,5534, and the standard deviation is 0,64483. In addition, within the framework of the multidimensional leadership orientations scale subscales, the mean score of political leadership is 3,9443 and its standard deviation is 0,74741, the mean score of human resources leadership is 4,3907 and its standard deviation is 0,61375, the mean score of charismatic leadership is 3,9901 and its standard deviation is 0,71828, and the mean score of structural leadership is 4,2082 and its standard deviation is 0,69924. was found. In this context, participants have high levels of self-liking, self-competence, political leadership and charismatic leadership; It can be said that the levels of human resources leadership and structural leadership are quite high. In addition, it was accepted that these variables exhibited normal distribution in terms of skewness and kurtosis values (see George and Mallery, 2010; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013).

Table 5: Age, Personal Income Level and Family Income Level Variables and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Analysis Results Between Scales

Variables	Self-Liking	Self-Competence	Political Leadership	Human Resources Leadership	Charismatic Leadership	Structural Leadership
Age	r	.064	.074	.132*	-.001	.147*
	p	.249	.183	.018	.990	.008
	n	322	322	322	322	322
Average Monthly Personal Income Level	r	.039	.078	.062	.039	.055
	p	.494	.169	.276	.496	.332
	n	310	310	310	310	310
Average Monthly Family Income Level (Including Personal Income)	r	.135*	.118*	.000	-.025	.016
	p	.020	.041	.996	.671	.784
	n	300	300	300	300	300

*p<0.05

According to Table 5, it was determined that there was a positive low level significant correlation between the age variable and the mean score of the political leadership ($r=0.132$) and charismatic leadership ($r=0.147$) subscales ($p<0.05$). In addition, it was found that there was a positive low level correlation between the mean scores of the subscales of self-liking ($r=0.135$) and self-competence ($r=0.118$) and the monthly average family income (including personal income) ($p<0.05$). However, no statistically significant correlation was found for other conditions related to the variables ($p>0.05$).

Table 6: t-Test Results According to Gender Variable

Subscales	Gender	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p
Self-Liking	Female	125	3.9780	.74749	321	-.289	.773
	Male	198	4.0013	.67591			
Self-Competence	Female	125	3.5860	.69296	321	.721	.471
	Male	198	3.5328	.61343			
Political Leadership	Female	125	4.0256	.70527	321	1.557	.120
	Male	198	3.8929	.77016			
Human Resources Leadership	Female	125	4.4624	.59537	321	1.673	.095
	Male	198	4.3455	.62230			
Charismatic Leadership	Female	125	3.9808	.71861	321	-.184	-.184
	Male	198	3.9960	.71983			
Structural Leadership	Female	125	4.1860	.72325	321	-.453	.651
	Male	198	4.2222	.68513			

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the scales in the context of the gender variable ($p > 0.05$).

Table 7: ANOVA Results According to Department Variable

Subscales	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Self-Liking	Coaching Education (1)	4.0000	.70918	322	1.425	.235	---
	Physical Education And Sports Teaching (2)	3.8947	.74694				
	Recreation (3)	3.9236	.70404				
	Sports Management (4)	4.0935	.67198				
Self-Competence	Coaching Education (1)	3.5538	.65475	322	1.745	.158	---
	Physical Education And Sports Teaching (2)	3.4539	.60117				
	Recreation (3)	3.4875	.64615				
	Sports Management (4)	3.6577	.65295				
Political Leadership	Coaching Education (1)	3.9200	.78086	322	1.546	.203	---
	Physical Education And Sports Teaching (2)	3.9474	.74405				
	Recreation (3)	3.8267	.75800				
	Sports Management (4)	4.0523	.71438				
Human Resources Leadership	Coaching Education (1)	4.4277	.57866	322	2.296	.078	---
	Physical Education And Sports Teaching (2)	4.4351	.59895				
	Recreation (3)	4.2489	.67860				

	Sports Management (4)	4.4613	.57385				
	Coaching Education (1)	3.9446	.66943				
Charismatic Leadership	Physical Education And Sports Teaching (2)	3.9404	.78737	322	4.210*	.006	4>3
	Recreation (3)	3.8289	.71677				
	Sports Management (4)	4.1730	.67876				
	Coaching Education (1)	4.2846	.60576				
Structural Leadership	Physical Education And Sports Teaching (2)	4.1228	.66333	322	5.018*	.002	4>3
	Recreation (3)	4.0111	.79668				
	Sports Management (4)	4.3671	.64475				

*p<0.05

According to Table 7, statistically significant differences were found between the charismatic leadership mean scores ($F_{(3-319)}=4.210$; $p<0.05$) and structural leadership mean scores ($F_{(3-319)}=5.018$; $p<0.05$) of the participants in the context of the department variable. Both of these significant differences were between the recreation and sports management departments and were found to be in favor of the sports management department. However, no statistically significant difference was found for other conditions related to the department variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 8: ANOVA Results According to Grade Variable

Subscales	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Self-Liking	1st Grade	3.9915	.71939				
	2nd Grade	3.9427	.68582	322	.509	.676	---
	3rd Grade	3.9923	.72277				
	4th Grade	4.0820	.69891				
Self-Competence	1st Grade	3.5057	.64963				
	2nd Grade	3.5665	.58743	322	.264	.851	---
	3rd Grade	3.5558	.73222				
	4th Grade	3.5963	.64887				
Political Leadership	1st Grade	3.8841	.71033				
	2nd Grade	3.9229	.79017	322	.508	.677	---
	3rd Grade	4.0185	.73885				
	4th Grade	3.9902	.73885				
Human Resources Leadership	1st Grade	4.3864	.65656				
	2nd Grade	4.3743	.63134	322	.206	.892	---
	3rd Grade	4.4431	.58255				
	4th Grade	4.3705	.55957				
Charismatic Leadership	1st Grade	3.8659	.77413				
	2nd Grade	4.0092	.74206	322	1.356	.256	---
	3rd Grade	4.0369	.60611				
	4th Grade	4.0852	.69422				
Structural Leadership	1st Grade	4.0966	.70856				
	2nd Grade	4.2018	.72287	322	1.630	.182	---
	3rd Grade	4.3462	.69834				
	4th Grade	4.2336	.62894				

When Table 8 is examined, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the scales in the context of the grade variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 9: ANOVA Results According to the Place of Residence Variable

Subscales	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Self-Liking	Village + Town + Community	3.9510	.66053	322	1.424	.242	---
	County Seat	3.8983	.69703				
	City Center	4.0470	.71587				
Self-Competence	Village + Town + Community	3.4902	.59731	322	.335	.716	---
	County Seat	3.5480	.60821				
	City Center	3.5733	.67516				
Political Leadership	Village + Town + Community	3.9137	.69886	322	.653	.521	---
	County Seat	4.0233	.74544				
	City Center	3.9161	.76226				
Human Resources Leadership	Village + Town + Community	4.5490	.46621	322	2.029	.133	---
	County Seat	4.3581	.66589				
	City Center	4.3624	.62045				
Charismatic Leadership	Village + Town + Community	3.9020	.71707	322	.461	.631	---
	County Seat	4.0140	.72650				
	City Center	4.0032	.71689				
Structural Leadership	Village + Town + Community	4.2108	.65836	322	.144	.866	---
	County Seat	4.2413	.73609				
	City Center	4.1922	.69580				

When Table 9 is examined, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the scales in the context of the place of residence variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 10: t-Test Results According to Actively Doing Sports Variable

Subscales	Actively Doing Sports Status	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p
Self-Liking	Yes	177	4.0692	.69837	321	2.177*	.030
	No	146	3.8990	.70057			
Self-Competence	Yes	177	3.6744	.65715	321	3.790*	.000
	No	146	3.4067	.59971			
Political Leadership	Yes	177	4.0531	.71645	321	2.915*	.004
	No	146	3.8123	.76518			
Human Resources Leadership	Yes	177	4.4169	.63025	321	.846	.398
	No	146	4.3589	.59372			
Charismatic Leadership	Yes	177	4.0734	.72003	321	2.312*	.021
	No	146	3.8890	.70546			
Structural Leadership	Yes	177	4.2853	.68865	321	2.195*	.029
	No	146	4.1147	.70290			

* $p<0.05$

When Table 10 is examined, it has been observed that there are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of participants' self-liking ($t_{(321)}=2.177$), self-competence ($t_{(321)}=3.790$), political leadership ($t_{(321)}=2.915$), charismatic leadership ($t_{(321)}=2.312$) and structural leadership ($t_{(321)}=2.195$) in the context of actively doing sports ($p<0.05$). It has been determined that all of these significant differences are in favor of those who do sports. However, no statistically significant difference was found between the mean scores of the human resources leadership sub-dimension ($p>0.05$).

Table 11: Results of Pearson Correlation Analysis Between Self-Esteem and Leadership

Variables	Political Leadership	Human Resources Leadership	Charismatic Leadership	Structural Leadership
Self-Liking	r	.338*	.356*	.444*
	p	.000	.000	.000
	n	323	323	323
Self-Competence	r	.424*	.241*	.538*
	p	.000	.000	.000
	n	323	323	323

* $p<0.05$

According to Table 11, it was determined that there were positive and moderately statistically significant correlations between the participants' mean scores of self-liking and political leadership ($r=0.338$), human resources leadership ($r=0.356$), charismatic leadership ($r=0.444$) and structural leadership ($r=0.470$) ($p<0.05$). In addition, it was found that there were positive and moderately statistically significant correlations between the self-competence mean scores of the participants and the mean scores of political leadership ($r=0.424$), charismatic leadership ($r=0.538$) and structural leadership ($r=0.426$) ($p<0.05$). On the other hand, it was understood that there was a statistically significant positive and low-level correlation between the participants' self-competence mean scores and their human resources leadership mean scores ($r=0.241$; $p<0.05$).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this section, comments/discussions regarding the findings related to the self-esteem and leadership levels of the students of the Faculty of Sport Sciences are given.

First of all, it was determined that there was a positive and low-level significant correlation between the age variable and the mean scores of the political leadership and charismatic leadership subscales. In this context, it can be said that as the age of the participants increases, their political and charismatic leadership levels also increase. Moreover, this situation can be associated with the experiences of individuals. Some studies have shown that age, experience, and maturity have an impact on preferred leader behaviors. In a study conducted by Chelladurai (1984); the subscales of preferred leadership behavior in basketball players aged 12-15 and 17-29 were compared. In the study, it was concluded that those in the younger age group preferred social support and democratic behavior more than the older players, while they tended to authoritarian behavior less. On the other hand, Car (2013) did not find a significant difference between the leadership orientation of the students taking sports education and the age variable.

In addition, it was found that there were positive and low-level significant correlations between the mean scores of the subscales of self-liking and self-competence and the monthly average family income (including personal income). In line with our findings, it can be stated that as the income increases, the self-liking and self-competence levels of the participants increase. In a study that differs from our research finding, Yanlic (2011) observed that the self-esteem of the participants did not change according to their monthly income.

On the other hand, there was no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the scales in the context of the gender variable. In Ustalar's (2019) study examining the self-esteem and shyness levels of secondary school students who do and do not do sports, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference in the self-esteem scores of the athletes according to gender. In the research of Korkmaz (2017) determined that

the gender variable did not play a decisive role on leadership orientation and organizational commitment levels. All these research results are similar to our research.

In another finding, it was found that there were statistically significant differences between the participants' charismatic leadership mean scores and structural leadership mean scores in the context of the department variable. Both of these significant differences were between the recreation and sports management departments and were found to be in favor of the sports management department. Within the scope of this finding, it can be said that the charismatic leadership and structural leadership levels of the students of the sports management department are higher than the students of the recreation department. This situation can be explained by the courses and leadership status of the students of the sports management department during the education process. Ozmutlu (2008) revealed that the leadership levels of Faculty of Sport Sciences students differed significantly according to the department variable. Aydin (2016) examined the leadership characteristics according to the department variable and found a significant difference. These findings in the literature are in line with our research findings.

It was observed that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the scales in the context of the grade variable. Karatas (2012) examined the empathic skills and self-esteem levels of Education Faculty students. As a result of the research, it was concluded that self-esteem did not show a significant difference in terms of grade variable.

In a similar finding, it was observed that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the scales in the context of the place of residence variable. Akcagoz (2017) examined the self-concept and depression status of working women. As a result of the research, it was concluded that the longest living unit variable did not show a statistically significant difference on self-concept. Avsaroglu and Ure (2007) found in their study that there was no statistically significant difference in terms of the variable of self-esteem, the longest living unit. All these findings support our research finding.

It was observed that there were statistically significant differences between the mean scores of participants' self-liking, self-competence, political leadership, charismatic leadership and structural leadership in the context of actively doing sports. It has been determined that all of these significant differences are in favor of those who do sports. This can be explained by the fact that individuals who do sports have high self-confidence and are strong both mentally and physically. In the study of Erman (2017), examining the self-esteem and social appearance anxiety levels of university students who do and do not do sports, it was seen that individuals who do sports under license have higher self-esteem than those who do not. In a study conducted on German youth, it is emphasized that encouraging young people to engage in physical activity and the decrease in body weight will positively affect the body esteem and body image of the youth, and will ensure that they are respected among their peers (Kirkcaldy et al., 2002). There are studies in the literature reporting that there is a directly proportional correlation between participating in sports activities and self-esteem (Karadag et al., 2008; Cam et al., 2000; Garry and Morrissey, 2000).

Finally, it was determined that there were positive and moderately significant correlations between the participants' mean scores of self-liking and political leadership, human resources leadership, charismatic leadership and structural leadership. In addition, it was found that there were positive and moderately statistically significant correlations between the self-competence mean scores of the participants and the mean scores of political leadership, charismatic leadership and structural leadership. In addition, it was understood that there was a statistically significant positive and low-level correlation between the participants' self-competence mean scores and their human resources leadership mean scores. When the findings are evaluated from a holistic perspective, it can be said that as the self-esteem of the participants increases, their leadership orientation also increases. In the study conducted by Li, Arvey, and Song (2011), it was seen that the self-esteem of individuals has a positive and significant effect on their leadership development and leadership styles. In the study conducted by Moran (2015), it was found that students' self-esteem levels had a significant effect on their leadership behaviors. In their study, Akdeniz and Saytekin (2020) determined that there is a positive and high level correlation between the inner self-esteem of sports science students and their leadership orientation. In the study conducted by Gunel (2021), on the students of the sports management department, it was determined that self-esteem has a positive and significant

effect on leadership orientations. These studies are consistent with the findings of our research. Individuals are motivated to maintain and develop their self-esteem (Shamir, 1991), which is based on a sense of competence and power/achievement (Gecas, 1982). In this context, the results are considered likely, since self-esteem functions as a motivation factor for leadership (Judge et al., 2002, Shamir & Howell, 1999).

As a result, it can be said that increasing the self-esteem of the participants is an important concept in the context of leadership orientations. Therefore, it is possible to increase the leadership orientation of the students of the faculty of sports sciences by directing them to activities that will increase their self-esteem. In this context, new information has been obtained that will contribute to the literature with the research findings. However, the results of the analysis include limited number of participant data considering the research group. For this reason, similar studies can be conducted with a large data set to cover all age groups. In addition, research results can be diversified by conducting qualitative, mixed and/or experimental studies on a research group with similar characteristics. In this context, different results can be reached that will contribute to the literature.

References

- Akcagoz, H. (2017). Investigation of Self-Concepts and Depression Status of Working Women. The Difference Between Self-Concept and Ideal Self-Concept and Determination of Depression Status in Terms of Variables, Master Thesis, Üsküdar University, Institute of Social Sciences, Istanbul.
- Akdeniz, H., & Saytekin, G. N. (2020). Examination of leadership orientations and self-confidence behaviors of faculty of sport sciences students (Kocaeli University Sample). *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 12, 233-250.
- Avsaroglu, S., & Ure, O. (2007). Investigation of self-esteem, decision-making and stress coping styles of university students in decision making in terms of self-esteem and some variables. *Selcuk University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 18, 85-100.
- Aydin, R. (2016). Comparison of Leadership Characteristics of Students Who are Engaged in Individual and Team Sports Studying at Physical Education and Sports Colleges. Master's Thesis, Bartın University, Institute of Educational Sciences, Bartın.
- Baumeister, R.F., Campbell, J.D., Krueger, J.I., & Vohs, K.D. (2003). Does high self-esteem cause better performance, interpersonal success, happiness, or healthier lifestyles? *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 4(1), 1-44.
- Bowker, A. (2006). The relationship between sports participation and self-esteem during early adolescence. *Canadian Journal of Behavioural Science*, 38(3), 214-229.
- Buyukozturk, S., Cakmak, E. K., Akgun, O. E., Karadeniz, S., & Demirel, F. (2020). Eğitimde Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri (29. Basım). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Cam, O, Khorshid, L., & Ozsoy, S.A. (2000). Investigation of self-esteem levels in a nursing school. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 1(8), 33-40.
- Car, B. (2013). Determination of Leadership Characteristics of University Students Receiving Sports Education. Master Thesis Gazi University Institute of Educational Sciences, Ankara.
- Chelladurai, P. (1984). Discrepancy between preferences and perceptions of leadership behavior and satisfaction of athletes in varying sports. *Journal of Sport Psychology*, 6, 27-41.
- Collins, N.M., Cromartie, F., Butler, S., & Bae, J. (2018). Effects of early sport participation on self-esteem and happiness. *The Sport Journal*, 20, 1-20.
- Coopersmith, S. (1967). *The antecedents of self-esteem*, (ss. 235-258) San Francisco: Freeman Press. Accessed from <https://archive.org> on 04.03.2020.
- Dogan, T. (2015). Two-Dimensional Self-Esteem: Adaptation of the Self-Liking/Self-Competence Scale into Turkish: A Validity and Reliability Study. *Education and Science*, 36(162), 126-137.
- Dursun, M., Gunay, M., & Yenel, I. F. (2019). Multidimensional Leadership Orientations Scale (MLOS): Validity and Reliability Study. *International Journal of Management Academy*, 2(2), 333-347.
- Erman, S. (2017). Investigation of Self-Esteem and Social Appearance Anxiety Levels of University Students Who Play and Don't Do Sports. Düzce University Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Physical Education and Sports, Master's Thesis, Düzce.
- Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. (2006). How to design and evaluate research in education (6th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill International Edition.
- Garry, J. P., & Morrissey, S. L. (2000). Team sports participation and risk-taking behaviours among a biracial middle school population. *Clin J Sport Med*, 10(3), 185-190.
- Gecas, V. (1982). The self-concept. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 8, 1-33.

- Gelbal, S., Duyan, V., & Sevin, C. (2010). Investigation of the Relationship between High School Students' Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Social Support Status and Self-Esteem Levels. *Journal of Social Work with Society*, 21(2), 7-18.
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2010). In GEN (Ed.), SPSS for Windows step by step. A simple study guide and reference. Boston, MA: Pearson Education, Inc, 10.
- Gunel, I. (2021). The Effect of Self-Esteem on Leadership Orientation: A Study on Students of Sports Management Department. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 7(1), 91-95.
- Hemphill, J., & Coons, A. (1957). Development of the Leader Behaviour Description Questionnaire, ed. R.M.Stogill- A.E. Coons, *Leader Behaviour: Its Description and Measurement*, Columbus: Ohio State University.
- Hersey, P., & Blanchard, K. (1988). *Management of Organizational Behavior: Utilizing Human Resources. Fifth Edition*, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Sf. 170-183.
- Jacobs, T. O., & Jaques, E. (1990). Military executive leadership. In K. E. Clark & M. B. Clark (Eds.), *Measures of leadership* (pp. 281–295). Leadership Library of America.
- Judge, T. A., Iliès, R., Bono, J. E., & Gerhardt, M. W. (2002). Personality and leadership: A qualitative and quantitative review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87, 765–780.
- Kagitcibasi, C., & Cemalcilar, Z. (2016). *Human and People from Past to Present Introduction to Social Psychology*. (16th Edition). Istanbul: Evrim Publications.
- Karadag, G., Guner, I. Cuhadar, D., & Ucan, O. (2008). Self-esteem of Gaziantep University Health School Nursing Students. *Firat Journal of Health Services*, 3(7), 29-42.
- Karatas, Z. (2012). Investigation of empathic skills and self-esteem levels of education faculty students. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Journal of the Faculty of Education*, 12(23), 97-114.
- Katz, D., & Kahn, R. L. (1978). *The social psychology of organizations*. New York: Wiley.
- Kets de Vries M. F. (2001). *Leadership in Organizations. International Encyclopedia of Social and Behavioral Science. INSEAD, France*.
- Kirkcaldy, B. D., Shephard, R. J., & Siefen, R. G. (2002). The relationship between physical activity and self-image and problem behaviour among adolescents. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol*, 37(11), 544-550.
- Koknel, O. (1982). *Personality from Anxiety to Happiness*. Istanbul: Altin Kitaplar Publications.
- Korkmaz, O. (2017). Authentic leadership and organizational trust. *The Journal of Academic Social Science Studies*, 58, 437-454.
- Li, W. -D., Arvey, R. D., & Song, Z. (2011). The influence of general mental ability, self-esteem and family socioeconomic status on leadership role occupancy and leader advancement: The moderating role of gender. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 22(3), 520-534.
- Moran, A. J. (2015). An examination of self-esteem's impact on the leadership behaviors of female undergraduate student leaders. Master Theses.
- Ozmutlu, I. (2008). Comparison of Leadership and Creativity Characteristics of Students Studying in Physical Education and Sports Colleges (Gazi University Example), Master Thesis Gazi University Institute of Health Sciences, Ankara.
- Ozoglu, S. (2019). Self concept in counseling. *Ankara University Journal of Faculty of Educational Sciences (JFES)*, 8(1) , 93-111.
- Rauch, C. F., & Behling, O. (1984). Functionalism: Basis for an alternate approach to the study of leadership. In J. G. Hunt, D. M. Hosking, C. A. Schriesheim, & R. Stewart (Eds.), *Leaders and managers: International perspectives on managerial behavior and leadership* (pp. 45-62). New York: Pergamon Press.
- Roberts, W. (1988). *Leadership Secrets of Attila The Hun*. Warner Books, New York.
- Rosenberg, M. (1965). *Society and Adolescent Self-Image*. Princeton University Pres, New Jersey.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016) *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach (7th Edition)*. West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Shamir, B. (1991). Meaning, Self and Motivation in Organizations. *Organization Studies*, 12(3), 405-424.
- Shamir, B., & Howell, J. M. (2018). Organizational and Contextual Influences on the Emergence and Effectiveness of Charismatic Leadership. Katz, I., Eilam-Shamir, G., Kark, R. and Berson, Y. (Ed.) *Leadership Now: Reflections on the Legacy of Boas Shamir (Monographs in Leadership and Management, Vol. 9)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Bingley, pp. 255-281.
- Slutzky, C. B., & Simpkins, S. D. (2009). The link between children's sport participation and self-esteem: Exploring the mediating role of sport self-concept. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 10(3), 381-389.
- Smith, R.E., Smoll, F.L., & Cumming, S.P. (2007). Effects of a motivational climate intervention for coaches on changes in young athletes' achievement goal orientations. *Journal of Clinical Sport Psychology*, 1(1), 23–46.
- Tabachnick, B.G., & Fidell, L.S. (2013). *Using multivariate statistics (6th ed.)*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Tafarodi, R. W., & Swann, W. B. (2001). Two-dimensional self-esteem: Theory and measurement. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 31(5), 653-673.

- Tufan, B. (1990). The concept of self-esteem and the development of self-esteem throughout life. *Journal of Hacettepe University School of Social Services*, 8(1-2-3).
- Ustalar, A. (2019). Investigation of Self-Esteem and Shyness Levels of Secondary School Students Who Do and Do Not Sports. Kütahya Dumlupınar University, Institute of Social Sciences, Department of Physical Education and Sports. Master Thesis. Kütahya.
- Yanlic, N. (2011). Self-Esteem of Disabled Athletes Playing Sitting Volleyball. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Fırat University, Institute of Health Sciences.
- Yorukoglu, A. (1985). Youth Mental Health and Mental Problems. Ankara: İş bank Cultural Publications.
- Yukl, G. A. (2010). *Leadership in Organizations. Seventh Edition, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.*